

Reviewing guidance on engaging communities in decisions relating to land

(Photograph from Tarland Community Garden, Courtesy of Annie McKee)

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Highlights

In 2018, the Scottish Government published '[Engaging communities in decisions relating to land: guidance](#)' in response to requirements on the part of Scottish Ministers within Part 4 of the Land Reform (Scotland) Act 2016. A strategic report on the effectiveness of the Guidance¹ is due in March 2026. This research aimed to provide policy teams with insights relating to the review they are undertaking to inform the 2026 report. Key findings include that:

1. There is a **lack of monitoring** of use of the 2018 Guidance on engaging communities in decisions relating to land and therefore lack of knowledge about its impact.
2. Most groups (including landowners, land managers, and communities) seem to have **low awareness of the Guidance**, and more awareness of the Scottish Land Commission's relevant Protocols, and other tools.
3. Key concepts for best practice in community engagement include **co-production and co-design**, which can facilitate more meaningful participation and are increasingly used in policy e.g., health and social care.
4. Good practice community engagement should seek to undertake careful analysis of who may be impacted by land-based decision making, including **broadening opportunities for engagement to marginalised and vulnerable people** and ensuring representation by diverse community groups.
5. More attention should be paid to the **risks associated with cumulative impacts**, in particular regarding engagement fatigue and ensuring a Just Transition, and routes for collaborative engagement processes.
6. Supports needed for best practice community engagement include **capacity building and training of land managers**. Requirements of large landowners under the Land Reform (Scotland) Act 2025 may require **supplementary guidance** because of the relative impact of their decisions.

¹ Referred to throughout this report as the '2018 Guidance' or the 'Guidance'.

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1. Introduction

In 2018, the Scottish Government published '[Engaging communities in decisions relating to land: guidance](#)', in response to requirements on the part of Scottish Ministers within Part 4 of the Land Reform (Scotland) Act 2016. A strategic report on the effectiveness of the Guidance is due in March 2026.

In 2016, the Scottish Government published a report on '[Engaging and empowering communities and stakeholders in rural land use and land management in Scotland](#)'. This report informed the Guidance on how best to assist rural communities to engage with decisions on land use and land management.

The last report regarding the Guidance (presented in 2021) relied on research by Ipsos MORI (in collaboration with SRUC), conducted during 2020, on [attitudes to land reform](#), which reported on survey findings relating to community engagement in land use decision-making. Whilst this research highlighted the need for awareness-raising with regard to how communities can become involved in land-based decision-making, the 2021 report concluded that there were no substantial updates necessary to require a full revision of the Guidance. Instead, the [Land Rights and Responsibilities Statement](#) (LRRS) was updated (Scottish Government, 2022), including revised wording to the principle relating to community engagement. Principle 6 in the original version of the LRRS (published in 2017) stated that "*There should be greater collaboration and community engagement in decisions about land.*" In 2022, that was revised to: "*There should be meaningful collaboration and community engagement in decisions about land*" (now Principle 7).

Given the time period since the Guidance was published, changes to the policy and legislative landscape and changes apparent within rural land management in Scotland, this report aims to provide policy teams with insights relating to the review they are undertaking to inform the 2026 report.

Project objectives

The Scottish Government's Land Reform Policy and Legislation Team requested that researchers at the James Hutton Institute compile any updates to the 2016 report, to inform the review of the 2018 Guidance.

This project aims to update:

- information on the policy landscape informing the statutory report.
- knowledge and advice relating to community engagement in decisions relating to rural land management in Scotland.

These updates will then be considered in relation to the current Guidance and whether they suggest any changes which might improve its effectiveness.

2. Methodology

This project has involved a targeted review of relevant academic and grey literature, with references identified through researcher experience, shared by members of the policy team, and via keyword searches for highly-relevant articles. These key words and search criteria are presented in Appendix 1.

The project team also contacted a small group of 'key informants'² whose professional experience was considered valuable to include in this review of evidence. These individuals were identified through researcher networks and through recommendations from members of the [Scotland's Land Reform Futures](#) project Stakeholder Advisory Group. The key informants included community engagement practitioners from the private, community, and third sector, as well as academics with research experience relating to community engagement. Eight key informants provided a short online interview and shared their perspectives on awareness, use and impact of the 2018 Guidance, suggestions for revision, and relevant updates to knowledge and best practice relating to community engagement in decisions relating to rural land management in Scotland³. Software-generated transcripts⁴ and researcher interview notes were coded thematically. The key informants also directed the project team to literature or published case studies that illustrate this updated understanding and may be relevant to the review report.

² Eleven individuals were contacted, with three declining to participate due to time availability. Please see a list of key informants in Appendix 5. Please note that all the key informants signed consent forms that indicated that they were happy to be included in a list of key informants in the report, but that their quotes and comments in the main text would not be attributed to them. Mark Reed expressed a wish that he was not anonymised in the main text and that he was credited for his contribution.

³ Please see interview guide in Appendix 4.

⁴ WebEx software was used to assist in the conversion of audio and video recordings of the interviews into text for thematic analysis.

3. Context and updates since the 2021 Review

An important starting point for reviewing the 2018 Guidance is to understand the key changes that have occurred since the 2021 report. Relevant policy and legislative changes therefore include:

- The implementation of the Land Reform (Scotland) Act 2016, including Part 5: the 'Right to Buy for Sustainable Development', that includes reference to the Guidance in determining outcomes in Part 5 Right to Buy processes (Ross, 2020).
- The Scottish Government's commitment to becoming a net-zero society by 2045 in addition to ensuring that the transition to a low carbon economy is 'just', conducted fairly and inclusively, and that it "*account[s] for the current injustices associated with land use in Scotland, and the wider challenges faced by many rural communities*" ([Scottish Government, 2021](#): 34).
- Revisions to the Land Rights and Responsibilities Statement (2022), including the revision of principle 7 relating to collaboration and community engagement.
- The establishment of the Register of Persons Holding a Controlled Interest in Land (2022), supporting increasing transparency in landownership.
- The development and passage of the Land Reform (Scotland) Act 2025, incorporating new requirements by owners and managers of large-scale landholdings, including the publication of Land Management Plans developed with community engagement.

In parallel to these policy changes, there is also evidence of a **changing pattern of landownership** in rural Scotland. This includes increasing ownership of land by community bodies (Scottish Government, 2025), but also evidence of increasing concentration of private landownership, including new types of **landowners motivated by natural capital markets and nature restoration** objectives (Merrell et al., 2025; Wightman, 2026). In response to this changing pattern of landownership, the Scottish Land Commission has developed and published guidance on [Delivering Community Benefits from Land](#) (2023), and the Scottish Government has similarly established [Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital](#) (2024), in particular that "*investors and land managers should engage with local communities in decisions about land and land use change, in line with the Scottish Government's Guidance on Engaging Communities in Decisions Relating to Land*".

3.1 Understanding public awareness and attitudes to land reform (since 2021)

The IPSOS-Mori and SRUC research on public awareness and attitudes to land reform (Warren et al., 2021) informed the 2021 report relating to the 2018 Guidance. Since 2021, key sources that help to inform public awareness and attitudes to land reform have been produced by the Scottish Land Commission, in particular their publication of findings from the [Community Engagement Baseline Surveys](#) (2022) and the [ScotLand Futures initiative](#) (report published in 2025). In 2022, 25% of community respondents to the Community Engagement Baseline Survey reported that they had 'little or no understanding of how decisions relating to land are made in their area', although this figure was reduced from 35% in 2019. Over 1200 people responded to the open call for contributions to the ScotLand Futures initiative. A key finding relevant to the Guidance is that: "*More than one in 10 people felt locked out of decisions about land use and want earlier, more meaningful involvement in shaping what happens locally*" (Scottish Land Commission, 2025: 13) and that: "*People called for earlier and more meaningful*

involvement in decisions, particularly around housing, renewable energy, forestry and large-scale investment projects” (Scottish Land Commission, 2025: 13).

3.2 Engaging and empowering communities and stakeholders in rural land use and land management in Scotland – Updates to the 2016 report

The [2016 report](#), produced by Diana Pound and colleagues at Dialogue Matters (including associate, Prof. Mark Reed⁵), was commissioned by the Scottish Government to understand the experience of those working with communities and stakeholders in land management, and to provide a framework for thinking about engagement and empowerment, including recommendations, for public bodies and environmental organisations. It was published before the final stage of the Land Reform (Scotland) Act 2016, including provisions for the 2018 Guidance.

We highlight the following key points from this report in considering what may be helpful to update with regard to the 2018 Guidance:

1. This report includes the following definition of community empowerment: “*communities being supported to do things for themselves; people having their voices heard in the planning and delivery of services [through] community engagement and participation*” (Pound et al., 2016: 2)⁶. The authors distinguish between ‘engagement’ processes and activities, which are designed to generate community ‘empowerment’. We suggest that **new definitions of ‘empowerment’ and ‘engagement’**⁷, as well as the inter-relationship between these two policy goals, are considered in relation to the 2018 Guidance.
2. The 2016 report is aimed at public bodies and other third sector environmental organisations and does not specifically focus on engagement by private landowners. The recommendations **do not entirely align with the changing pattern of Scottish landownership** (e.g. including new institutional landowners; see Section 3), or private landowners of whom more is demanded with regard to community engagement, following the Land Reform (Scotland) Acts in 2016 and 2025. For example, the section on transitioning ‘organisational culture’ for public bodies may not be relevant for private landowners with few or no staff. Likewise, ‘applying the empowerment framework’ refers only to public bodies and third sector organisations. The recommendations are entirely aimed at public bodies and would require substantial resources to implement.
3. The 2016 report includes **a valuable overview of the types of power** held by environmental organisations (Pound et al., 2016: Annex 5). In considering the 2018 Guidance, it might be helpful to consider developing a similar analysis of power held by other landowning organisations in Scotland⁸ (see also Pound et al., 2025: Annex 6).

⁵ Prof. Reed was a key informant in this research; please see Appendix 5 for further details regarding his consent to be named in the report.

⁶ Please note that the link provided to the original Scottish Government source for this definition is no longer available (originally from 2015).

⁷ See for example: [695fc7b605544_SLC-protocols-definitions.pdf](#)

⁸ This analysis may be best undertaken as a separate research project (as recommended by Pound et al., 2025), informed by literature review and interviews with key actors. It is not included in this report.

4. This report also provides tables and links to further resources regarding methods and forms of engagement (Pound et al., 2016: 25-26 and Annex 6). It might be valuable to compare the range of methods and engagement approaches with those mentioned by key informants (see Section 5.3), to **identify more contemporary engagement options**⁹. Examples may include greater utilisation of digital platforms and online communication within community engagement processes, but the key informants note that further training is needed to ensure good practice in online engagement approaches, and that they must be offered in conjunction with 'offline' and in-person options.

⁹ See also recent research published on best practice landscape governance by Diana Pound and colleagues: [Landscape-Futures-governance-and-justice-final-report-.pdf](#)

4. Insights from community engagement literature and case studies

- Research since 2021 shows community respondents want **earlier, more meaningful involvement** in local land use decision making.
- Relevant literature relating to community engagement in land use decision-making in Scotland highlights its benefits, including **better environmental governance outcomes and wider acceptance of land use change**.
- Literature also highlights persistent barriers, in particular with regard to **power inequalities that inhibit effective and good practice** community engagement processes.
- People may be prevented from participating in community engagement processes due to **society-wide structural inequalities** but strategies can address these inequalities.

Scottish land reform appears to be of interest to academics internationally, not least due to the distinct approach to community landownership that is promoted within Scotland (see: [McMorran et al., 2020](#); Lovett, 2020; [Hoffman, 2013](#)). Despite this, there is relatively little academic literature or published empirical research that deals directly with questions of community engagement in land-based decision-making in rural Scotland (see: [McKee, 2015](#)¹⁰), or that has been published since the 2021 report relating to the Guidance. There is, however, a new focus on the influence and impact of natural capital investment, nature restoration, and the ‘just transition’ in Scottish land use. This research provides insights relating to good practice community engagement, as well as risks and challenges, which are summarised below.

4.1 Benefits from and Barriers to Engagement

In 2023, the Agile Initiative published ‘[A Recipe for Engagement in Nature-based Solution and Nature Recovery](#)’ that provides adaptable guidance and case studies relevant to policy-makers, landowners and managers, non-governmental organisations, community groups and researchers (Hafferty et al., 2023). The ‘Recipe for Engagement’ defines engagement as ‘*a process by which individuals, groups and organisations choose to take an active role in decisions which affect them*’, stating this can include a wide range of approaches (Hafferty et al., 2023:7). The value of engagement in the context of nature-based solutions is emphasised, highlighting that engagement can lead to better environmental governance outcomes, a more holistic knowledge of environmental systems and how to monitor them, and the promotion of the “(co-)ownership of land and natural resource” (Hafferty et al., 2023:9)¹¹. A complementary report commissioned by Natural England (Pound et al., 2025) details evidence of good governance in landscape change, and the necessary components to achieving ‘Best Practice Dialogue’, which includes: “*fostering co-design and delivery of landscape change working with multiple other stakeholders and communities, with a collaborative, power sharing and inclusive ethos; and applying procedural justice principles: contextual fit; scalar fit; conflict resolution;*

¹⁰ The research reported in this paper was also the basis for the document ‘[Working Together for Sustainable Estate Communities](#)’, linked in the Resources section of the 2018 Guidance, and this document might also benefit from contemporary review and revision.

¹¹ Hafferty et al. (2023) also presents a series of case studies across the UK to exemplify good practice in community engagement and elaborates on each ‘ingredient’ of engagement in detail.

neutral facilitation; free, prior, and informed consent; integrating knowledge systems; and adaptable and flexible processes” (Pound et al., 2025: no page number).

In the context of rewilding, community engagement can achieve ‘wider social acceptability’ and a ‘conceptual shift within Scottish rewilding discourse’ is increasingly emphasising the role of local communities, public ‘engagement’ and ‘involvement’ (Martin et al., 2023: 80; Martin et al., 2021; Brown et al., 2025). There is growing interest in and experience of partnership-working within rewilding and conservation projects, involving private and public sectors and communities, as well as cases where rewilding projects have been driven by communities themselves¹². The research by Martin and colleagues, however, highlights the tensions that can emerge within engagement processes, between prioritising local community interests and the wider public, or environmental interests, as described: *“Interviewees questioned whether communities had the expertise or would inevitably become focused on more local issues, often perceived as likely to prioritise social and economic concerns rather than (or at expense of) the environment e.g., biodiversity”* (Martin et al. 2023, p.84). The authors also concluded that in their analysis of rewilding projects in Scotland: *“There was a widely held aspiration that communities should be involved in how land is managed, but a significant gap in practice”* (Martin et al., 2023:85). According to their analysis, Martin and colleagues believed that there was a lack of meaningful community engagement, with participation largely focussed on ‘convincing communities to agree with pre-determined choices’, and critically that decision-making power remained with landowning organisations.

Brown and colleagues also highlight ‘fundamental barriers’ to the realisation of a Just Transition in rural Scotland relating in part to a lack of *“meaningful participation of local people in land-use decision-making”*¹³ (Brown et al., 2025: 1855). In order to achieve *“a transformative approach to just transitions”* (and fulfil Scottish policy goals), it was necessary to overcome historical injustices, and widen *“democratic involvement of communities”* in land governance (Brown et al., 2025: 1855), which they perceive to be at risk due to reports of tokenistic engagement processes and deepening power inequalities arising from private investments into natural capital and carbon offsetting (see also Pound et al., 2025). Brown and colleagues espouse the need for communities to demand *“new spaces of participation...and spaces of representation”* (Newell et al., 2023 in Brown et al., 2025: 1857), and to support community capacity in agenda-setting around landscape restoration and just transitions. Pound et al. (2025) similarly emphasise the importance of building awareness, understanding and practical guidance (including tools and training) regarding **procedural justice in landscape governance** (i.e. fairness and transparency in decision-making and dispute resolution processes).

4.2 Case Study Research in Scotland

Through qualitative analysis of six case studies of private landowner and rural community partnership working, underpinned by the theory of Communicative Action, McKee (2015) illustrated the potential mutual benefits of good practice community engagement and partnership working, but also that the key constraint to partnerships could be summarised as inequality, with associated community disempowerment. This research illustrated the

¹² Martin et al. (2023) highlight the Langholm Initiative Tarras Valley Nature Reserve and the Loch Arkaig Community Forest as two key examples.

¹³ Indeed, Brown et al. (2025) highlights ‘material barriers to engagement’ in the case studies investigated, which reinforced inequalities in community participation.

importance of institutions and governance that seeks to reduce the ‘polarisation of power’ in contexts of Scottish landownership, and that supports community empowerment.

This research is reflected in the findings of Scottish Government-commissioned research on the [social and economic impacts of green land investment in rural Scotland](#) (McKee et al., 2023), which demonstrated a spectrum of community-landowner engagement experiences, ranging from perceived good practice to perceived poor practice. The latter was generally associated with insufficient community engagement or consultation, contributing to a lack of community involvement in land use decision-making. Analysis of qualitative data from six case studies of green land investment across rural Scotland also highlighted concerns regarding the persistence of unequal social hierarchies despite landownership and land use change, the relative power and influence of green land investor-owners, and a perceived lack of awareness by green land investor-owners of local culture and valuing local knowledge. Interviewees believed that local people would want to have greater involvement in land use decision-making if long-term goals for land management were clear, which has implications for the development of Land Management Plans on implementation of the Land Reform (Scotland) Act 2025.

Follow-up research on [community engagement in land use decision-making](#) (Beingessner et al., 2024) confirmed these findings and the desire for participatory decision-making, community engagement, inclusion, and transparency and accountability. Community members pointed to the power that landowners have to set terms of engagement and communications and a lack of procedures for communities to proactively engage, making engagement a ‘one-way street’. They suggested a broader definition of community than those in the landholding’s immediate vicinity, as different land use decisions may require different boundaries for consultations e.g., flooding concerns may affect an entire watershed, or consideration of one windfarm may need to be in context of other windfarms already in the area. Inclusion of those who may be harder to reach or are heard less was also considered important. For all of this to happen, more transparency about ownership and the ability to contact owners is needed.

4.3 Overcoming inequalities and ensuring equality in community engagement

Mark Reed and colleagues also highlight ongoing debates within community engagement research and practice, including regarding what the implications of engagement mean in terms of (in)equity, trust, power relations, and ‘whose reality counts’ (Reed et al., 2024). This critique extends to the contested understandings and ethical issues surrounding the term ‘stakeholder’ (which often encompasses diverse knowledge types and communities), in particular that it can maintain power imbalances, disregard local and indigenous knowledge, and refers to histories of colonisation and dispossession. Reed and colleagues propose that *“the framing of engagement...must, at its heart, challenge normative assumptions that people are willing, able and, indeed, obliged to engage”* (Reed et al., 2024; no page number).

Research on community engagement in Scotland, with a particular focus on so-called ‘hard to reach’ voices, found that people are typically prevented from participating in community engagement processes due to society-wide structural inequalities (Lightbody et al., 2017). These inequalities include: education, confidence, resources, responsibilities (i.e. work and caring), language barriers, and disabilities; and they can be reproduced in community engagement settings (see: Lightbody and Escobar, 2021). Furthermore, the long-term and negative consequences of community engagement are ‘rarely documented’ (Lightbody, 2017:

11; Lightbody and Escobar, 2021), thus limiting opportunities for corrective action. Effective strategies to overcome inequalities and ensure equality in community engagement are described by Lightbody, including that:

- *“There is no one-size-fits-all approach.*
- *Hybrid approaches can be more useful in reaching a wider audience and overcoming obstacles, this includes top-down processes organised by policy makers as well as bottom-up initiatives shaped by communities.*
- *Partnerships must continue to be forged with government, public services, third and community sectors, and a range of professional groups in order to share information so that the expertise of many are shaping future community engagement processes.*
- *Strategic Community Assessment and available descriptive statistics of local demographics...will offer more insights into challenges facing particular communities and equalities groups.*
- *Auditing community engagement offers a closer and more telling analysis of who takes part and who is missing out. Highlighting who is missing will help shape recruitment and sampling techniques for participatory and deliberative processes in the future. However, this is not problem-free.*
- *Using democratic innovations, such as participatory budgeting and mini-publics, to involve ‘easy-to-ignore’ groups can improve future processes by ensuring diversity. Heterogeneous groups can offer a different form of insight into public opinion and represent the wider public through random or stratified sampling. However, homogenous groups can also offer insight into what they want or need from community projects and perhaps offer explanations for why groups can be reluctant to get involved in mainstream processes.*
- *Offering incentives and/or financial compensation can open community engagement up to a wider demographic and lower the barriers to participation for the most disadvantaged.*
- *Technology can make participation easier, more enjoyable and more accessible, but it can also create new divides and inequalities. Using the Census and other data sources to predict and recognise patterns is necessary for ongoing action.*
- *There is evidence to suggest that citizens who have a stake and a voice in their communities will be more likely to invest in long-term engagement and less alienated from local developments” (Lightbody, 2017:20).*

4.4 Community engagement standards for environmental land-use decision-making

These empirical projects align with reviews undertaken with the goal of developing community engagement standards associated with environmental land-use decision-making (including nature restoration) (David et al., 2023), and natural capital markets, such as the Facility for Investment Ready Nature in Scotland (FIRNS) [Community Inclusion Standard](#)¹⁴. The Standard was informed by an extensive literature review on [‘Community participation for community benefits from natural capital projects’](#) (Hannon et al., 2024). Hannon and colleagues include a broad definition of community, incorporating concepts of communities of place and of

¹⁴ See also: Nixseaman and Cook (2023): https://1a81854e-93f7-41cd-8125-cde1965840a3.filesusr.com/ugd/9ac930_3e11e9feccb84adea05e04cd153bc067.pdf?ref=natcert.earth

interest¹⁵. Their review also provides a comprehensive description of models of community participation, including deliberative and participatory democracy; contemporary community engagement framework; an overview of challenges and routes to address barriers to community participation; and summaries of current practitioner guidance, including the Scottish Land Commission’s Protocol relating to the Guidance. Hannon et al. (2024) also present ten key principles to guide effective community participation¹⁶. These are presented in the following Box 1.

¹⁵ “A collective of people who are connected through a shared sense of identity, which is distinctive either in terms of: (a) place, such as a defined geographical boundary; and/or (b) practice, such as shared interests, motivations and values” (Hannon et al., 2024: ii).

¹⁶ See also the ‘recommendations for best practice’ summarised by Davis et al., 2023: [Nattergal+Report+on+Stakeholder+Engagement+Best+Practice.pdf](#)

Box 1: Ten key principles to guide effective community participation for community benefits in natural capital projects (from Hannon et al., 2024: 56)

1. **Bespoke:** conscious of – and responsive to – a community’s unique characteristics, capacities and capabilities when considering approaches for inclusion and participation and benefits generation. This includes activities to raise awareness of project plans and opportunities to participate.
2. **Legitimate and democratic:** able to offer equitable and consensual participation that has been codesigned with communities and is built upon a relationship of trust and power-sharing.
3. **Inclusive:** accessible to all, including reducing physical and social barriers to participation. It should also be sensitive to existing imbalances of power and resource – both present and historical.
4. **Coordinated:** developed alongside existing frameworks such as community action plans, and cognisant of other projects and initiatives requiring community input. This is particularly important to support integrated ‘joined up’ activity to deliver broader community benefits and to reduce engagement fatigue.
5. **Resourced:** aware that the developer and the stakeholders may need to be upskilled to ensure full understanding of the value, purpose, and importance of community benefit and participation, its principles and potential. Communities and developers may both need capability building or resourcing training, or capacity bolstering through paid staff.
6. **Lasting:** embedding routes to maximise community benefit from the conception of the project will support community needs to be reflected in the development. Participation should be conducted in partnership with trusted gatekeepers in a way that establishes a long-term presence (physical, virtual etc.) to build lasting relationships with the community.
7. **Proportionate:** the depth and scale of community participation should be commensurate with the potential for community influence or say over project outcomes, and the commitment and aspirations towards community benefits.
8. **Targeted, timely and longitudinal:** early engagement and participation pathways are important to align proceedings with community needs and priorities. Participation may not necessarily be long-term and regular - it may be appropriate at points to have short-term engagement. Timings should be responsive to coordination with other community initiatives to reduce or remove the participatory burden. Community input can take place indirectly through alignment and coordination with other initiatives.
9. **Transparent:** the methodology, rationale and purpose of participation, as well as the rationale and evidence base for final decision-making (including the scope of influence of the community) should be transparent from the outset.
10. **Accountable and reflexive:** participatory processes – and their associated outcomes – should be independently monitored and evaluated for fairness, transparency, and outcomes, to inform reflexive learning about how activities can work best and how success is defined.

This overview of selected relevant literature relating to community engagement in land use decision-making in Scotland highlights persistent barriers, in particular with regard to power inequalities that inhibit effective and good practice community engagement processes.

As detailed in the following section based on the key informant interviews, a review of the 2018 Guidance could involve critical attention to reducing unethical practices and power imbalances, and overcoming inequalities that inhibit good practice community engagement in decisions relating to land in Scotland and thus promoting community empowerment.

5. Insights from key informant interviews

- The Guidance is not often referred to in the day-to-day work of key informants, and **awareness is considered to be low among landowners, land managers, and rural and urban communities.**
- There has been an increase in community expectations of engagement which the Guidance may underpin, but **monitoring of its use is required to assess impact.**
- Current best practice approaches to community engagement include **co-production and co-design, as well as using more inclusive processes to identify participants**, to facilitate more meaningful and effective participation.
- Recommended revisions to the Guidance include utilising it to **collate and streamline other statutory guidance protocols, signposting resources and case studies**, and including **guidance on new forms of engagement** e.g., online engagement.
- **Capacity building and training** for all involved in decision-making is a key support needed for effective community engagement.
- The Land Reform (Scotland) Act 2025 may necessitate **supplementary guidance for the owners and managers of large (>1,000ha) landholdings.**

5.1 Awareness and use of the Guidance

The **key informants** were asked to describe **their awareness and use of the 2018 Guidance** in their professional and personal experience. Most mentioned that they had ‘re-read’ the Guidance before the interview, or that they had previously referred to it extensively, but that they **did not now often refer to it in their day-to-day work**, instead looking at their own organisational toolkits or the [Scottish Land Commission’s Community Engagement Protocol](#). Some explained that they refer to the Guidance for considering the impact of a situation and the level of engagement that should happen in different situations, in particular using the ‘impact’ diagram¹⁷ (Diagram A – ‘When should I engage’) as an annex in their own community engagement plans to show the ‘thought process’.

The key informants highlighted the **important role of the Scottish Land Commission’s Protocol**, and mention that they regularly use and recommend others also refer to this document, for example in supporting community decisions relating to land. The Scottish Land Commission’s Protocol is also drawn upon extensively in the first draft of the Facility for Investment Ready Nature in Scotland (FIRNS) [Community Inclusion Standard](#), which in turn formed the basis for the BSI Flex 705 ‘Nature markets – Community engagement and benefits from natural capital projects’.

Awareness and use of the Guidance by landowners and land managers

Many of the key informants believed that there had been **a significant shift in awareness, understanding, and willingness** on the part of landowners and land managers to undertake good practice community engagement, in particular since the Guidance was first published in 2018. Landowners and land managers reportedly find the concept of community engagement easier to understand than other parts of the Land Rights and Responsibilities Statement.

¹⁷ Diagram A – ‘When should I engage’ (page 13 of 2018 Guidance for Engaging Communities in Decisions Relating to Land, Scottish Government).

Community engagement has become normalised and landowner and land manager attitudes appear to have “*changed a lot from ‘why should we do that’ to ‘how can we do this better?’*”

An indicator of increasing awareness regarding the need to undertake good practice community engagement in decisions relating to land has been the **uptake of training** available from organisations such as Planning Aid Scotland and developed by private land agencies such as Savills.

Nonetheless, despite this ‘cultural change’, **awareness of the Scottish Government’s 2018 Guidance is thought to be relatively low** in comparison to the ‘best practice advice’ available from the Scottish Land Commission and membership organisations such as Scottish Land & Estates and Community Land Scotland. Some key informants believe that there may be **confusion** on the part of landowners and land managers regarding what has been published by the Scottish Government or the Scottish Land Commission, what is statutory, and what could impact on them in the future.

The Scottish Land Commission’s community engagement surveys (undertaken in 2019 and 2022) indicated an increase in terms of landowner and land manager awareness of the Guidance, but key informants suggested that there may be **less experience of landowners and land managers using or applying the Guidance**. There appears to be some ‘**resistance**’ to adhering to the Guidance and other protocols where landowners and land managers are already going through a statutory process (e.g., relating to planning processes or forestry), and a tendency for land managers to undertake the ‘bare minimum standard’ of engagement required by the statutory process. Experiences shared by key informants relating to forestry illustrate a lack of early-stage community engagement and processes aligned with ‘consultation’ rather than best practice engagement.

Mark Reed mentioned that in his experience, natural capital investors (or ‘green land investment’ owners; see McKee et al., 2023) follow community engagement guidance available in the markets in which they are investing. Whilst many see community engagement as a cost, there is growing awareness of the risk of reputational harm resulting from poor community engagement. One route to influence community engagement practices by these types of developers and landowners is therefore to replicate best practice guidance into the Woodland and Peatland Codes, in order to make community engagement a requirement of registration.

Awareness and use of the Guidance by rural and urban communities

Key informants agreed that in the most part, **rural and urban communities were generally ‘less aware’ of the Guidance**; as described: “*I don’t think anyone from a community perspective has ever mentioned the Guidance to me in any form of community engagement session.*” An exception may be when community groups and members of the public believe that they have not been consulted properly in a decision relating to land, in which case they **may refer to the Guidance to highlight perceived flaws in a community engagement process**. If a community group were engaged in a land-related decision, they are likely to access the Guidance as a matter of course, in particular if they are also receiving support or guidance from organisations such as Development Trusts Association Scotland or Community

Land Scotland. Similar to the level of awareness on the part of landowners and land managers, people are considered to be more likely to be aware of the Scottish Land Commission's Community Engagement Protocol in the 'community space', but not in the 'public space'.

As indicated in the Scottish Land Commission's community engagement surveys, urban communities tend to see land reform and community engagement as a rural issue, and therefore less relevant in an urban context. Findings from the Scottish Land Commission's community engagement surveys also indicated more awareness where a survey response was received from a community organisation than from an individual.

5.2 Guidance underpinning improvement in community engagement practice

The key informants provided insights into how the 2018 Guidance has influenced community engagement in decisions relating to land. As mentioned above, it is believed that community engagement has become more normalised, and in some contexts, **community engagement practice has improved** (e.g. within natural capital investment contexts). Key informants report **a shift in community expectations regarding engagement, which may be underpinned by the Guidance**, and that it may have formalised processes of community engagement that were already ongoing¹⁸. However, it is considered difficult to assess the use and impact of the 2018 Guidance: *"It probably has influenced engagement by creating a certain bedrock expectation...of the approach that you should take...A bedrock that we don't recognise is there anymore"*.

A critical issue, therefore, in understanding the impact and role of the Guidance is the **lack of consistent monitoring of the use of the Guidance** and examples that clearly demonstrate the type/extent of the influence of the Guidance in community engagement processes relating to land. This is highlighted as a challenge to assessing the impact of community engagement guidance in other policy sectors (e.g. health and social care). The Scottish Land Commission have reportedly not gathered any information on whether the 2018 Guidance has been influential in the case studies of community engagement that the Commission has collated. As one key informant asserts: *"Unless there is an attempt to monitor how it's used, then we can't really comment confidently on the impact...[and] if we don't routinely monitor it, then it becomes very patchy and anecdotal."*

Some key informants believed that whilst the Guidance will have encouraged more community engagement (i.e. in terms of quantity), it might **not have necessarily improved quality**, and related documents such as the Scottish Land Commission Protocol or guidance produced by Scottish Land & Estates may have had a more significant influence on improving community engagement practice. It is suggested that the formalisation of the Guidance risks community engagement being considered a 'tick box' exercise that can impact on quality, for example: *"I've done everything it says in the Guidance that I need to do' but actually did you have quality engagement with people? Did you have open...dialogue where people felt comfortable and willing to open up about their genuine feelings on things?"*

¹⁸ Some key informants were concerned that the Guidance has 'potentially made people nervous about doing something they always did', in case of making mistakes, and therefore also not undertaking engagement willingly. Increased training provision, for example by the Scottish Land Commission, is requested (see also Section 5.5).

Indeed, there are ongoing issues reported to the Scottish Land Commission regarding **poor quality community engagement**, in particular relating to failures in recognising and taking into account cumulative impacts of land use change, leading to engagement fatigue¹⁹ within communities. As described: “A developer on their own...even if they were looking at protocols and following good practice...might not take into account that actually [there are] four other developments in the area and the overall...a massive impact on communities.” It is also suggested that the **understanding of ‘impact’** outlined in the Guidance needs further attention by landowners and developers, considering in more depth the impact on communities rather than their own project timelines or bottom line.

5.3 Improving the effectiveness of Guidance

The key informants were asked to share their knowledge and experience of key concepts and approaches to community engagement that may not have been discussed or applied when the Guidance was originally published in 2018. A summary of these concepts and approaches, and how they relate to the Guidance are considered below.

Co-production and co-design

Key informants explained that in their experience, best practice involves early engagement and ‘genuinely inviting the community to give new ideas, rather than solely seeking approval for landowner or manager goals’. It was also explained that in referring to [Arnstein’s Ladder of Participation](#), good practice would involve moving from ‘lower rungs’ that relate to coercive approaches, through meaningful participation, towards the ‘gold standard’ of **co-production**. The language of ‘co-production’ is considered to increasingly be adopted within policy, for example, as demonstrated in [‘Planning with People’](#) produced by the Scottish health and social care sector. Relatedly there is increasing understanding and awareness of the value of **‘lived experience contributions’**, including good practice examples where: “people with lived experience have a voice within the organisation and the priorities that are set and how those priorities are delivered on”.

Co-design is described as working with communities in a ‘meaningful way’ (i.e. respectfully and valuing their contribution) from the outset of a project and aiming for equitable partnerships between communities and landowners/developers. Engagement in this context therefore includes communities ‘setting the agenda’, bringing in community knowledge, and being involved in decision-making. Pound et al. (2025) also highlight the **importance of ‘co-delivery’**, i.e. that co-production and co-design also involve the sharing of power, resources, and responsibility in implementing change, and the co-design of solutions (see also: Lloyd-Evans et al., 2023).

Community mapping and the Three ‘I’s’ Analysis²⁰

Key informants highlighted the importance of **‘community mapping’**, which involves identifying “*who the community are, and what their needs [are] and actually who actually represents...the community or doesn’t represent the community*”. Considering the different

¹⁹ Based on the research team’s experience, we also highlight the difference between engagement fatigue relating to being ‘over-engaged’ versus engagement not being seen as influencing or leading to change in decision-making processes.

²⁰ A framework for developing good practice community engagement that includes as an explicit focus the impact on groups in environmental decision-making processes (see Reed et al., 2025).

groups within a community and the range of different routes necessary to engage meaningfully with these different groups is the basis for good practice community engagement. Key informants also described related approaches within communications and marketing regarding identifying appropriate ‘channels for different audiences’ or ‘end users’. There is also an emphasis on focussing on inequalities and disadvantage within this community mapping exercise, in particular considering marginalised, under-represented, and vulnerable groups, who are often over-looked and may be more significantly impacted by land-based developments. The use of **equality impact assessments** may be appropriate here to improve community mapping and achieve good practice community engagement.

Mark Reed and colleagues have developed a “*radically inclusive approach to systematically identifying who to engage with and how to prioritise limited engagement resources*”, which is called the ‘**Three I’s Analysis**’²¹. This framework for developing good practice community engagement processes includes the explicit focus on groups who will be impacted by decisions relating to land (or environmental decision-making processes as described in Reed et al., 2025). As one key informant explained, “*communities that have been labelled as ‘hard to reach’...are experts of their problems as well as the solutions*”. As Mark explained: “*It’s not just who has most interest, who has most influence, what about those who are impacted, who don’t have any interests, who don’t even know the things happening until it impacts them, and who by definition have NO influence but who we should be engaging with*”. Adopting this approach would support the prioritisation of engagement with marginalised and vulnerable groups, where relevant, through a process of ‘analysis’, rather than as part of a ‘checklist’²².

A focus on ethics

Within the current Guidance, there are appendices that provide an overview of the human rights-based approach and other legal requirements relating to ‘engaging communities in decisions relating to land’. Some key informants asserted that ‘more needs to be done to translate the human rights-based approach into practice on the ground’, and also to think more deeply around the ethics of engagement, in particular with vulnerable and marginalised groups who may be negatively impacted if there is poor community engagement (e.g. through ‘tick box’ approaches). This relates to a shift in approach and ethical standards also underway in social research, in particular relating to addressing extractive modes of research. As Mark Reed explained: “*I think we need to consider is the **procedures, mechanics, the governments, the accountability** around this. It’s one thing to tell people this is what you should be doing, but actually when this comes to ethics, in the same way that we do research ethics, we should be doing engagement and impact. And if government expects people to engage, they should also expect that to be done ethically. And there need to be **checks and balances and systems** to ensure that this is done.*”

In research, and in other contexts of community participation, it is increasingly important that there is direct benefit to participants for their contribution, for example through financial remuneration or other rewards for their time. It is recognised that there are difficulties in

²¹ See: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0301479724034236?via%3Dihub> (Reed et al., 2025).

²² A recent newsletter from the ‘Agriculture for Net Zero’ network also stated that with regard to community engagement in food system transformation: “*Recruitment from diverse and under-represented voices, particularly in rural areas, should be seen as a pre-requisite to successful engagement projects, rather than an add on*”. Available online: <https://www.agrifood4netzero.net/2026/02/12/the-power-of-people-how-deep-community-engagement-is-a-driver-of-food-systems-change/> [Accessed: 17.2.26; Last updated 12.2.26]

providing this type of remuneration, not least funding available to provide payments, but also ensuring that those participating are able to be remunerated, and this does not become an unintentional barrier to engagement (e.g. where payment may interfere with the receipt of benefits)²³. There is also an important balance between ‘legitimate volunteering’ of time in community engagement processes, as well as seeking to ‘level the playing field’ and remove barriers to engagement²⁴.

5.4 Revising the Guidance to support best practice community engagement

The key informants provided valuable suggestions regarding how the 2018 Guidance could be revised to better support best practice community engagement in decisions relating to land. These suggestions include:

1. Raising awareness of the Guidance;
2. Providing more signposting to other resources and case studies;
3. Including guidance on pre-engagement, online engagement, and engaging with young people;
4. Revising the definitions of key terms, including proportionality and significant impact;
5. Providing routes to recourse by communities and managing expectations; as well as
6. Greater consideration of the Just Transition.

Final specific suggestions relating to revising the Guidance are also outlined.

1. Raising awareness of the Guidance

As mentioned above, key informants believed that there was a relatively low level of awareness of the Guidance by landowners, land managers, and communities. Some suggested that the Scottish Government could play a bigger role in providing more direct promotion of the Guidance, which may ‘carry more weight and encourage greater attention’. Further opportunities for raising awareness include:

- Royal Institution of Chartered Surveyors (RICS) rural meetings and land agent training days (e.g. Savills Resident Agent training days), as well as via rural-focussed solicitors, who will be supporting clients working through engagement processes. There is also the opportunity for the Scottish Land Commission to provide more direct advice to land agents and influence good practice. It was noted that professional bodies would likely publish information regarding any revision to the Guidance, in particular if aspects become mandatory (e.g. relating to the provisions in the Land Reform (Scotland) Act 2025; see Section 5.6).
- Through membership organisations, such as Scottish Land & Estates, Development Trusts Association Scotland, and Community Land Scotland.
- Through raising awareness within other policy areas and amongst public sector leadership, as described: *“from a government point of view, it would be really good to see them promote it more with public bodies, but also within the government*

²³ The Scottish Government has published related guidance: [Research - paying participant expenses and compensating for time: guidance - gov.scot](#)

²⁴ See the case studies detailed in McLean (2021): [Paying people with lived experience for their participation](#)

itself...Different areas of government might operate in their own way or have their own targets to meet and not necessarily pay attention to other voluntary bits of work from elsewhere, so it would be good to see the government push that themselves. And... with the public bodies that they sponsor...show leadership [and] set the example that they're looking for other people to follow."

Mark Reed suggested that **further consideration of 'carrot and stick'** approaches to ensure good practice community engagement, including requiring good practice community engagement prior to natural capital project validation, or penalties if people do not meet good practice standards. He also emphasised that "**changing the image of engagement as a cost to business...to actually not engaging is the real risk and in the long term you saved yourself money and hassle by doing good community engagement**". The likely financial benefits of community engagement, in particular in the planning process²⁵, was also highlighted by other key informants as a route to raising awareness of the Guidance.

2. Providing more signposting to other resources and case studies

Key informants emphasised the need to 'streamline' the volume of statutory guidance, protocols, and best practice documents, and develop a 'one stop shop' for people to quickly access what they need regarding good practice community engagement in decisions relating to land. This could involve making more prominent links in the Guidance to other key resources (rather than including them only in the Appendices), such as the [National Standards for Community Engagement](#), the 'Visioning Outcomes in Community Engagement' (VOiCE) software, Planning Aid Scotland's [SP=EED Framework](#), guidance relating to the development of Local Place Plans, and indeed, the Scottish Land Commission's recently revised [Community Engagement Protocol](#). Materials developed by private companies and consultants that provide specialist community engagement training to landowners, land managers, and natural capital investors, may also be relevant.

Including case studies in the Guidance was also considered a route to support good practice, as described: "*the production of [good] practice examples is a very worthy endeavour because it does help other people build their own skills, knowledge, and capacity*". Case studies have been collated by the Scottish Land Commission, Scottish Land & Estates, and are promoted by private landowners and consultants²⁶. Prominent examples mentioned by key informants included the experience of creating a community land use plan at Applecross, the engagement undertaken by Buccleuch Estates prior to land sales at Langholm, community engagement undertaken by Bute Estates, and Corrou Estate (in conjunction with St Andrews University), as well as the development of the Memorandum of Understanding between Highlands Rewilding and the Tayvallich Initiative²⁷. Other examples may be considered 'early adopters', as described: "*some landowners that...have been more at the forefront of developing...community engagement and doing more collaborative style work with communities so they might be a good starting point*".

²⁵ The financial costs and benefits of community engagement in planning processes are described in Wright and Tolson (2020): [See1fa960b190_20200611_SLC_REPORT_Value_of_Early_Engagement_in_Planning.pdf](#)

²⁶ See for example: [Helping It Happen Case Studies | Scottish Land & Estates](#); [Projects - Sylvestris](#); [Our Work — Lucy Laidlaw Communication](#); [Community engagement and inclusion — Highlands Rewilding](#)

²⁷ See: [Memorandum of Understanding: A roadmap to aligning community, nature and shareholder interests — Highlands Rewilding](#) [Accessed: 4.2.26]; see also: McIntosh (2023).

3. Including guidance on pre-engagement, online engagement, and engaging with young people

Several key informants explained that in their opinion the Guidance did not sufficiently emphasise the **value of pre-, ongoing, or early engagement**²⁸, and helping people to understand ‘the need for engagement before you start engaging’, in particular in building relationships and trust. As explained: “...*the Government guidance is really helpful in setting out, you know, significant impact and what to do when things are changing, but...we felt like it was missing something about that engagement to build a relationship, even if you're not making changes*”. Key informants also highlighted the value of finding out in advance ‘what ways people want to engage’ and reviewing approaches to community engagement in light of this type of pre-engagement.

In light of the changes to working patterns and the increase in the **use of online communication tools** during and following the Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic, key informants suggested that the Guidance include detail on holding community engagement events online and making best use of online tools and digital platforms (e.g., survey platforms), in conjunction with in-person or ‘analogue’ approaches such as paper surveys (with pre-paid return envelopes). There are perceived benefits to a ‘hybrid’ approach involving both online and in-person events, in particular due to the opportunity of broadening participation to those who may otherwise be prevented or discouraged from attending. Traditional approaches to community engagement, such as ‘village hall’ consultation events can inhibit open and honest engagement, whilst longer ‘drop-in’ events are at times considered more productive and support ongoing and pre-engagement processes.

Key informants also highlighted the need for more explicit advice in the Guidance regarding **engaging with children and young people** in decisions relating to land, in alignment with requirements in Local Place Plan development. They believed that ‘young people are not being factored into traditional engagement processes’, and that these would not likely attract young people to engage (e.g., attending community council meetings), in contrast to undertaking engagement sessions directly with schools, for example.

4. Revising the definitions of key terms, including proportionality and significant impact

Key informants also highlighted the **importance of consistency of language** used throughout the Guidance, ensuring that it is clear who exactly is to take action (e.g. tenants vs. those with the ability to make decisions over land). Reviewing understandings and definitions of ‘**proportionality**’ and ‘**significant impact**’ may be necessary in revising the current Guidance. Mark Reed explained that “*taking an evidence-based approach to this often sets the bar too high*” with regard to community engagement, and that to ensure uptake by the private sector (e.g. natural capital investors) focussing on achieving ‘good’ rather than ‘best practice’, may be necessary, in particular in contexts where there is clear community benefit. Similarly, reviewing the criteria for what may be considered ‘significant’, for example, in

²⁸ See also: Wright and Tolson (2020): [See1fa960b190_20200611_SLC_REPORT_Value_of_Early_Engagement_in_Planning.pdf](#)

contexts of cumulative impact, would be beneficial, with key informants highlighting the role and value of pre-existing relationships between landowners and communities in understanding 'significant impacts'.

5. Providing routes to recourse by communities and managing expectations

At present, the Guidance does not describe any **route for recourse on the part of communities** if they believe that engagement processes have been insufficient or conducted below good practice standards. As described: *"When it comes to guidance and the legal requirement to consult, for example...if there is no appeals process, then it...can remove a recourse for communities where they feel they're not heard"*.²⁹ On this point, we refer back to the suggestion of developing co-production and co-design as core concepts in good practice community engagement, in particular that communities are involved with setting the decision-making agenda around land and in determining appropriate community engagement processes.

Key informants suggested that the Guidance should add further detail regarding **managing expectations on the part of communities**, seeking to avoid situations where engagement misleads communities or unnecessarily raises expectations (i.e. that engagement is a process of sharing between parties, and does not give a veto to communities). Good practice community engagement should be 'well scoped', with timelines presented at the beginning of a process, including early engagement stages, proposed engagement methods, ensuring sufficient time is provided for communities to consider ideas and plan to attend engagement events, as well as transparency around decision-making processes, and how community input can influence decision-making. It is anticipated that this scoping process would also involve consideration of how to deal with conflict and could therefore reduce the risk of conflict arising. Furthermore, it is important that communities are informed of actions arising from engagement processes, and that recommendations made by communities are implemented, in particular to enhance trusting relationships between partners.

Some also highlighted the need to provide '**protocols and good practice guidance for communities**' with regard to expectations of their role and behaviour: *"Engagement requires something of everybody and that it isn't just all on the landowner to do it that the communities do have to both engage positively with it or at least not nastily, if they don't agree with what's happening then fair enough, but to engage with respect, I suppose."* Landowner expectations should also be managed with regard to achieving community consensus on decisions relating to land.

6. Considering the Just Transition

Key informants stated that **greater consideration of the Just Transition** in a revised version of the Guidance may support more 'joined-up thinking and a proactive approach' on the part of landowners and land managers, helping to avoid consultation fatigue and recognising the time and effort that some communities are being asked to put into engagement processes. As

²⁹ It is acknowledged that in such cases, communities and/or landowners can now consult the Scottish Land Commission Good Practice Advisors to support positive resolution, and it is likely that this will be a key role for the new Land and Communities Commissioner.

described: “if people carrying out these activities were a bit more mindful of what else was going on in an area...and connecting to what communities are already doing, that might help”. As outlined in the following Section 5.5, it was suggested that communities are given further **support to enable their involvement in engagement processes**, in particular relating to the **energy transition**.

Final specific suggestions for revisions to the current Guidance were also proposed:

- Paragraphs 22 and 47 gives examples of **representative community organisations**. It is suggested that ‘community development trust’ is added as a specific example of this type of organisation.
- It is suggested that within paragraph 28 on ‘benefits of engagement’, the **value of engagement to ‘opening up channels of communication’** between landowners and communities and increasing community confidence in approaching the landowner at a later date, should be made more explicit.
- Paragraph 33 indicates that the power of deciding the appropriate community engagement process in a local context sits with the landowner. This is in stark contrast to the recommendations of key informants regarding best practice approaches to community engagement, in particular that **landowners ask communities about appropriate engagement approaches** (i.e. during pre-engagement and ongoing engagement processes).
- Paragraphs 40 and 41 give examples of what may be considered ‘cumulative impact’, and suggest that businesses and local/public authorities ‘think about’ the combined impact of their activities, and ‘try’ to minimise negative impacts. It is suggested that the revised Guidance should **engage more critically with issues of cumulative impact** and suggest ways that multiple landowners could coordinate engagement processes and consider the downstream or wider effects of the proposed land-based activity, which may extend the geographical community with whom to engage (see: Beingsner et al., 2024).
- Paragraphs 46 and 47 give suggestions regarding identifying who may be impacted by a decision relating to land, and therefore who should be engaged with. There is a risk that the landowner or land manager’s perspective of the ‘right people’ is not representative of the wider community, that some people become ‘gatekeepers’, and that ‘representative’ groups are made scapegoats for unpopular decisions. This is also a risk in the Guidance stated in paragraph 56. It is suggested that the revised Guidance encourages landowners and land managers to **invite all those who may consider themselves likely to be affected** by land-based decision-making, as well as giving more attention to ensuring representation from ‘hard to reach’ groups (with reference to the Three ‘I’s’ Analysis; see Section 5.3).
- Paragraph 58 describes practical barriers faced by people that prevent their participation in engagement activities. The literature review and key informants describe a **much wider range of barriers to engagement**, and it is suggested that this section is expanded on in a revised version of the Guidance. As one key informant explained, the “*wider range of barriers also requires...multiple, complex or creative ways of increasing participation*”.
- With regard to Diagram B – ‘How to Engage’, it may be **questioned whether all of the methods under ‘informal engagement’ can be defined as ‘engagement’** rather than one-way communication. Regular communication is important, but there is a risk

that one-way communication methods become standardised as ‘good practice’. The key informants reiterated that resources and **further information regarding formal methods of engagement are linked with in Diagram B** and made more prominent earlier in the Guidance (rather than only in the final references section).

5.5 How can best practice community engagement in decisions relating to land be supported?

The key informants provided their recommendations regarding what is needed to support best practice community engagement, highlighting areas that with increased resourcing and capacity could promote Scottish Government policy goals relating to community empowerment and land reform.

Many of the key informants highlighted the **importance of capacity building and training for all involved in land-based decision-making** (including private, community and public land managers, such as local authorities) with regard to best practice community engagement, and a perceived gap in training availability. Good practice community engagement training would build confidence, knowledge, and skills, through demonstrating different types of community engagement opportunities (including early engagement) and how they should be designed, in order to broaden opportunities for engagement³⁰. In conjunction with the production of revised Guidance, key informants also recommend a ‘national upskilling programme’, including shared learning or peer-support approaches, that can help to overcome the ‘fear factor’ and develop skills to deal with the ‘complexities, nuances, and ethics’ of community engagement in practice. Key informants shared examples of community engagement training provided in other sectors (e.g. community development, social research), that involved ongoing support through good practice and ‘alumni’ networks.

Key informants also suggest that higher and further education providers who are training future land managers could do more to **embed community engagement as a core skill**, as well as develop knowledge regarding legal requirements.

Training programmes relating to community engagement in decisions relating to land should also consider issues relating to **dealing with contentious or complex developments, managing conflict (i.e. with and within communities), and conflicts of interest**. Skilled and professional facilitation may be necessary to avoid (re)inflaming community conflicts, and acquiring these skills go beyond engaging with written guidance documents.

Key informants also highlighted the **key role of the Scottish Land Commissions Good Practice Advisers**, and the previously dedicated ‘community engagement advisors’ (whose role is now within the Good Practice team, given the wider remit of the Land Rights and Responsibilities Statement). Increasing this capacity and reinstating the dedicated ‘community engagement advisors’ was recommended by the key informants.

There is also a need for **communities to have access to facilitation, skills, and other**

³⁰ Savills have developed a training programme that involves working through case studies of different community engagement approaches and scenarios, for trainees to identify opportunities and appropriate actions.

support (e.g. from voluntary services, enterprise agencies, etc.) to enable them to participate in engagement processes, in particular relating to complicated or difficult projects, e.g. large-scale energy infrastructure developments. Community-led processes such as the **development of Local Place Plans should also be well supported and resourced** as a route to identifying community priorities. Communities should be encouraged to involve early engagement with landowners, and landowners encouraged to ‘get involved’ in the development of local place plans, to achieve mutually beneficial outcomes. Key informants also highlighted the need for more work on community engagement in urban settings (e.g., overcoming issues of transparency and accessibility of land and property owners), contributing more ‘thought’ and policy support to promote and encourage engagement and transparency in urban contexts.

5.6 Improving the Guidance with regard to the Land Reform (Scotland) Act 2025

The Land Reform (Scotland) Act 2025 includes requirements for community engagement regarding the development of land management plans for landholdings over 1000 hectares (ha)³¹. Key informants shared their views on how the current Guidance could be revised to accommodate these new requirements, and what resources would be helpful to landowners and communities to fulfil these new requirements.

In the first instance, key informants requested **clarity regarding the expectations of land management plans**, what is necessary to include and what people are expected to deliver. When considering community engagement in the context of large-scale landholdings, key informants explained that ‘from a practical perspective, your community is potentially larger’, there may be multiple communities of place, or there may be no community (e.g., due to geographical remoteness). This brings challenges relating to ensuring community representation, which may be resolved through approaches to community mapping and the ‘Three I’s Analysis’ described in Section 5.3.

One key informant suggested the **development of supplementary guidance for the owners of land over 1000ha**, as well as “*a programme of kind of awareness raising, maybe webinars, workshops, training with communities and landowners to help them understand the requirements and how things work in terms of reporting and you know for communities, how they should address a problem if they encounter it*”; this may be part of role for the new Land and Communities Commissioner.

Guidance to be produced by the Scottish Government to inform the development of land management plans should include **templates, case studies, and signposting** to existing good practice in community engagement (see Section 5.4). It was suggested that holding workshops with representatives from the National Farmers Union for Scotland (NFUS) and Scottish Land & Estates may help to identify what is needed in the new Guidance to provide support relating to the implementation of the new legislation. Some key informants said that the Scottish Government need to reassure landowners that their business interests and confidentiality will be respected (i.e. maintaining this expectation from the 2018 Guidance).

³¹ A hectare (ha) is a metric unit of area that is equal to 10,000 square metres. It is commonly used for measuring large plots of land, such as agricultural fields and forests. One hectare is also equivalent to approximately 2.471 acres. See: onlineunitconverters.com

The key informants highlighted the **importance of considering ‘joined-up engagement’** as described in the 2018 Guidance, and the need for local development plans, local place plans, community-led action plans, and the new land management plans to align, cross-reference, or at least signpost to the other documents, and to avoid duplication. The development of land management plans should involve understanding the wider ‘planscape’ and recognise *“community priorities where they have been expressed already”*. Recognising that there will be ‘varying degrees of ability for landowners to resource community engagement relating to land management plans’, there should be resources provided ‘through the system’ to support the development and alignment of local place plans and land management plans.

Despite the mandatory community engagement requirements in the Land Reform (Scotland) Act 2025, key informants believe that there **remains a need for voluntary good practice** (for all landowners, regardless of landholding size), and that the 2018 Guidance should be updated before secondary legislation relating to the land management plans. Some suggest that the revised Guidance should ‘influence what comes through in terms of requirements for engagement with the Act’, and that standards should be raised in forthcoming secondary legislation: *“people should be required to go a little bit further”*. This relates to the finding of the Scottish Land Commission’s investigation into impact of scale and concentration of landownership (Glenn et al., 2019), and the significant influence that large-scale landowners can have with regard to housing, employment, and community wealth-building, prompting the suggestion that *“we should expect a higher threshold”* and standard of engagement. It is also suggested that to **overcome limitations to community engagement in relation to legislative compliance**, the Scottish Government need to consider a *“a genuine offer of support to take people through the process”*, for example working with place-based third-sector organisations who are better equipped and have close relationships with communities.

6. Conclusions

This research has sought to gather knowledge and insights to inform the statutory report on the effectiveness of the [Engaging communities in decisions relating to land: guidance](#) (Scottish Government, 2018). This report summarises the key changes that have occurred since the 2021 report, including relevant policy and legislative changes, and **highlights the changing pattern of landownership in Scotland**, in particular relating to developing natural capital markets. Understanding of public awareness and attitudes to land reform, and community engagement in decisions relating to land, are drawn from the Scottish Land Commission's Community Engagement Surveys (2019 and 2022), as well as the recent ScotLand Futures initiative (report published in 2025). A targeted review of relevant academic and grey literature also highlights how **the changing nature of landownership**, in particular the focus on natural capital investment and nature restoration, **requires evaluation of community engagement practice** by rural land owners, managers, and developers. Questions arise relating to persistent power imbalances and challenges to the achievement of a Just Transition in Scottish land use. Principles for 'effective community participation for community benefits in natural capital projects' are shared, as well as mechanisms to overcome issues of inequality in engagement processes. Key findings from the literature review also include that:

- Research since 2021 shows community respondents want **earlier, more meaningful involvement** in local land use decision making.
- Relevant literature relating to community engagement in land use decision-making in Scotland highlights its benefits, including **better environmental governance outcomes and wider acceptance of land use change**.
- Literature also highlights persistent barriers, in particular with regard to **power inequalities that inhibit effective and good practice** community engagement processes.
- People may be prevented from participating in community engagement processes due to **society-wide structural inequalities** but strategies can address these inequalities.

This research also reports on the perspectives of eight 'key informant' community engagement practitioners with regard to their awareness and use of the 2018 Guidance, what they believe has been the role and impact of the Guidance, and opportunities to improve its effectiveness. The key informants also described contemporary understandings and approaches to community engagement that may not have been considered during the initial development of the 2018 Guidance, and the types of resources and support required to ensure good practice community engagement is undertaken across Scotland. Finally, the key informants provided suggestions for how the Guidance could be revised in light of new provisions for community engagement in the Land Reform (Scotland) Act 2025. Key informant insights are thus summarised:

1. There is a **lack of monitoring** of use of the 2018 Guidance on engaging communities in decisions relating to land and therefore lack of knowledge about its impact.
2. Most groups (including landowners, land managers, and communities) seem to have **low awareness of the Guidance**, and more awareness of the Scottish Land Commission's relevant Protocols, and other tools.
3. Key concepts for best practice in community engagement include **co-production and co-design**, which can facilitate more meaningful participation and are increasingly used in policy e.g., health and social care.
4. Good practice community engagement should seek to undertake careful analysis of who may be impacted by land-based decision making, including **broadening opportunities for engagement to marginalised and vulnerable people** and ensuring representation by diverse community groups.
5. More attention should be paid to the **risks associated with cumulative impacts**, in particular regarding engagement fatigue and ensuring a Just Transition, and routes for collaborative engagement processes.
6. Supports needed for best practice community engagement include **capacity building and training of land managers**. Requirements of large landowners under the Land Reform (Scotland) Act 2025 may require **supplementary guidance** because of the relative impact of their decisions.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Keywords and search criteria for literature review

Date range – 2016 – 2025/6 [inclusive] – aiming to capture literature that has been published since the last review.

Keywords:

Community engagement + land [use / management / planning]

Community engagement + land reform

Community engagement + landownership

Co-development + land

Appreciative inquiry + land

Stakeholder engagement + land

Stakeholder participation + land

Community participation + land

Attitudes / views + land reform

Community empowerment + land

Appendix 2: Participant information sheet

Project information

Reviewing guidance on engaging communities in decisions relating to land

Timescale: January 2026

Funding body: Scottish Government

Version: 7/1/2026³²

What is this project about?

In 2018, the Scottish Government published '[Engaging communities in decisions relating to land: guidance](#)'. This 2018 guidance document now needs to be reviewed with a report due in March 2026.

In 2016, the Scottish Government published a report on '[Engaging and empowering communities and stakeholders in rural land use and land management in Scotland](#)'. This report informed the guidance on how best to assist rural communities to engage with decisions on land use and land management.

The last report regarding the Guidance (presented in 2021) relied on the Ipsos MORI research, conducted during 2020, on [attitudes to land reform](#), which reported on survey findings relating to community engagement in land use decision-making.

Objective

The Scottish Government's Land Reform Policy and Legislation Team have requested that researchers at the James Hutton Institute compile any updates to the 2016 report, and that may inform the review of the 2018 guidance. Anticipated updates will include:

- Updates to the policy landscape informing the statutory report.
- Updated knowledge/advice relating to community engagement in decisions relating to rural land management in Scotland.

These updates will then be considered in relation to the current guidance and whether they suggest any changes which might improve the effectiveness of it.

How will information be gathered?

This project will largely be desk-based, including a review of relevant academic and grey literature. We will also contact a small group of 'key informants' whose professional experience would be valuable to include in this review of evidence. These key informants will include community engagement practitioners and representatives of relevant Scottish land organisations. The key informants will be invited to provide a short online interview (45-50 minutes) to discuss updates to knowledge and advice relating to community

³² Please note that there have been minor amendments to this version since it was circulated to the key informant interviewees, in particular regarding references to the Scottish Government's statutory report.

engagement in decisions relating to rural land management in Scotland. We will also ask the key informants to direct us to literature or published case studies that illustrate this updated understanding and may be relevant to the statutory report.

How will the interviews take place?

The interviews will take place via WebEx (a video-conferencing platform), at the date and time of the participant's choosing, before mid-January 2026. They will be audio and video recorded and transcribed using WebEx.

Do I have to take part?

No, your participation is voluntary, and you can withdraw at any time, up until the point that we publish the research findings (March 2026). We do not anticipate any risks to you from your participation. Even if you agree to take part in the interview, you can choose not to answer a question(s), without having to give a reason.

We hope that participation may be of value to the key informants as a route to sharing their practical understanding with policymakers and informing updates to the statutory guidance. This may have implications for the implementation of the Land Reform (Scotland) Act 2016 and the Land Reform (Scotland) Act 2025.

Data confidentiality

All data will be treated with full confidentiality. Please note that the draft report to the Scottish Government will include a list of the 'key informant' interviewees, but no comments will be directly attributed to individual interviewees. All identifying information in the body of the report will be removed. Participants will be able to opt out of having their name included in this list and will have the chance to review the final report prior to publication.

Data will be stored on restricted-access, password protected secure systems through the James Hutton Institute. Our privacy notice: <https://www.hutton.ac.uk/privacy-notice/> has more detail about how your data is handled.

What if I want to withdraw?

If you would like to withdraw your data at any point up until the publication of the research outputs (March 2026), please contact the lead researcher in this project.

Who can I contact?

If you have any questions at any time, please feel free to contact **Annie McKee** annie.mckee@hutton.ac.uk – Tel. **01224 395294**

The Hutton research team also includes: Naomi Beingessner, Sam Poskitt, and Louise Jacquemain. The Scottish Government Advisor is Emma MacCallum, Rural and Environmental Science and Analytical Services (RESAS) division.

Appendix 3: Interview consent form

RESEARCH CONSENT FORM

Participant Identification Number:

Title of Project:	Reviewing guidance on engaging communities in decisions relating to land
Principal Investigator:	Dr Annie McKee
Study Number:	James Hutton Institute Project code: KUC-F01-29 PAWSA Land Reform

Please Initial Box

I confirm that I have read, or had read to me, and understand the participant information sheet (dated: 7.1.2026) relating to the above study. I have had the opportunity to ask questions and these have been answered fully and explicitly.	
I understand that my participation is voluntary, and I am free to withdraw at any time, without providing any reason and without my legal rights being affected, up until the publication of any outputs. If I choose to withdraw during or after the interview / workshop and up until publication, my data will be omitted.	
I understand the study is being conducted by researchers from The James Hutton Institute, and funded by the Scottish Government.	
Any personal data collected via this consent form as well as the interview recording and transcript will be kept confidential within the research team and stored securely. <i>Please note that the draft report to the Scottish Government will include a list of the 'key informant' interviewees, but no comments will be directly attributed to individual interviewees. All identifying information in the body of the report will be removed. Participants will be able to opt out of having their name included in this list and will have the chance review the final report prior to publication.</i>	
I understand that the interview will be audio recorded and transcribed using WebEx software. Due to the recording being undertaken via WebEx, I understand that a video will also be made that will feature my face, which will be deleted at the end of the project.	
I agree for my data to be used in outputs relating to this study (e.g. a report for the Scottish Government, oral presentations, etc).	
I agree to being contacted at a later date in relation to this study.	
I acknowledge that I have read and understood the privacy notice.	
I agree to take part in the above study.	

Name of Participant (please print)

Signature

Date

PI/Researcher Name (please print)

Signature

Date

Privacy Notice

The James Hutton Institute (“Hutton”) will use your personal data for the purposes of the research undertaken in the project ‘Reviewing guidance on engaging communities in decisions relating to land’.

Hutton is the data controller for the personal data collected from participants which it processes for the purposes of the project.

Our lawful basis under the UK GDPR for processing your personal data is that this is necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest in relation to research funded by the Scottish Government.

For the purposes of this project, we may process the following types of personal data about you:

- Name
- Contact details (telephone number, email address)
- Any information we collect from you or hold about you as part of this research project, i) data collected during the interview; ii) project management documentation e.g., consent forms and iii) records of communications with you e.g., email correspondence.

Your personal data will be stored securely on the computer systems of the James Hutton Institute and any access to it will be restricted only to the project team. We will store and retain any information that we collect from you as part of this research project for up to five years after the end of the project, to allow all publications based on this work to be accepted for publication.

If you have given your consent to being contacted at a later date in relation to this study, we will retain your name and contact details for five years after the end of the project. We will contact you on an annual basis to confirm this ongoing consent.

If you have agreed for your online interview to be recorded, personal data captured within the recording are stored within the cloud service owned by the video-conferencing company. Your personal data may be transferred outside of the EEA and the UK by the video-conferencing company. We have in place appropriate contracts with any third-party suppliers who may be accessing your data on our behalf to ensure that your data is held securely and protected adequately.

You have rights in relation to your personal data. Our main privacy notice, <https://www.hutton.ac.uk/privacy-notice/> (Hutton) explains in more detail how we handle your personal data as well as your rights. Any requests for accessing the personal information which we hold about you (“Subject Access Requests”) can be addressed to SAR@hutton.ac.uk.

If you have any questions about the research or a complaint about how we have handled your personal information, please get in touch with annie.mckee@hutton.ac.uk. If this does not resolve your complaint, you can contact the Hutton Data Protection Officer on dpo@hutton.ac.uk.

The Information Commissioner is the regulator for UK GDPR. You have the right to raise concerns with the Commissioner if you are not happy with the way your information is being handled:

Customer Contact
Information Commissioner's Office
Wycliffe House
Water Lane City
Wilmslow
SK9 5AF

You can also report concerns online. For more information, please see the Contact Us page of their website: <https://ico.org.uk/global/contact-us/>

Principal Investigator contact details:

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Appendix 4: Key informant interview guide

Introduction for participants³³

Thank you very much for giving us your time and at short notice – we are very grateful. We will aim to finish within 45-50 minutes.

As outlined in the invitation email and participant information sheet, the Scottish Government's Scottish Government's Land Reform Policy Team to provide a report that helps to inform the statutory report regarding the 'Engaging communities in decisions relating to land: guidance' (originally published in 2018). The Land Reform (Scotland) Act 2016 includes a duty that the effectiveness of this guidance is reviewed within a five-year period following the last review in 2021.

The policy team have asked researchers at the James Hutton Institute to provide additional support to their own review, in particular through a literature review and small set of interviews with community engagement experts and practitioners. We are referring to the interviewees as 'key informants'. This interview will seek to gather your thoughts and experience of using the current Scottish Government Guidance, the use and awareness of the guidance by other groups, and your suggestions for how the Guidance can or should be improved.

As outlined in the participant information sheet and consent form, your data is confidential and we will not attribute comments directly to key informants in our report to policy. We will include a list of the 'key informants' in the report, but you can choose to opt out of having your name included in this list if you wish. Prior to publication (which we anticipate will be in March), you can review the final report. We will share our draft report with policy by the end of January.

Do you have any questions at this stage? Are you happy for us to press record for notetaking purposes?

Thank you.

Introduction

Please can we start with your own introduction and an overview of your role and experience in community engagement relating to land?

Awareness of the Guidance

Please can you describe your awareness and use of the current guidance for engaging communities in decisions relating to land? [Ask for examples]

To what extent do you think landowners, land managers, tenants, rural and urban communities are aware of the current guidance?

[Do you think that the wider public are aware of the guidance? How could this awareness be improved?] (If time allows)

³³ Please note that there have been minor amendments to this introduction since it was provided to the key informant interviewees, in particular regarding references to the Scottish Government's statutory report.

Role of the Guidance

In your experience, how does the Guidance influence community engagement in decisions relating to land? Please can you give any examples?

[Direct SG question:]

To what extent is the amount and quality of engagement with communities over decisions relating to land improving or not improving? Have the Guidance or the documents drawn from the Guidance played a role in this?

Improving the Guidance

What is your understanding of current best practice for community engagement? What are the key concepts or approaches that you are aware of today that may not have been discussed or applied when the Guidance was initially published in 2018?

What is needed to better support best practice community engagement?/How can policymakers better support best practice community engagement?

How do you think the Guidance could be revised to better support best practice community engagement?

[Direct SG questions]: [Prompts to questions above]

- Are there aspects of community engagement that are not currently covered by the Guidance?
- Are there areas that are included but not relevant in practice?
- Are there aspects that require updating or revision?

Can you give any examples or share case studies that indicate how the Guidance could be improved or updated?

Improving the Guidance with regard to the Land Reform (Scotland) Act 2026

You will be aware that the new Land Reform (Scotland) Act 2025 includes requirements for community engagement regarding the development of land management plans for landholdings over 1000ha. Do you have any suggestions for how the current Guidance could be revised to accommodate these new requirements?

What do you think the best resources are to help landowners and communities to fulfil these new requirements? Do engagement approaches need to be adapted for different landholding scales?

Wrapping up

Do you have any further thoughts or suggestions? Is there anything you thought we would talk about that we have not?

Thank you very much for your help and support for this research.

[If time, reiterate timeline as in introduction.]

Appendix 5: Key informants

Gemma Campbell, Scottish Land Commission

Lucy Laidlaw, Lucy Laidlaw Communication

Debbie Mackay, Savills

David McAllister, Planning Aid Scotland

Duncan MacPherson, Community Development Consultant

Dr Esther Oenga, University of Reading

Susan Paxton, Scottish Community Development Centre

Prof. Mark Reed, Scotland's Rural College

Please note that all the key informants signed consent forms that indicated that they were happy to be included in a list of key informants in the report, but that their quotes and comments in the main text would not be attributed to them. Mark Reed expressed a wish that he was not anonymised in the main text and that he was credited for his contribution.

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